
Quantum Chemical Analysis of the relationships between electronic structure and dopamine D₁ and D₅ receptor binding affinities in a series of 1-phenylbenzazepines

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Abstract The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez QSAR equation was employed for searching formal quantitative relationships between the electronic structures of a group of 1-phenylbenzazepines and their affinities for the dopamine D₁ and D₅ receptors. The electronic structure was calculated with the Gaussian 16 software after a full geometry optimization. A linear multiple regression analysis was carried out by using the common skeleton approach and 20 local atomic reactivity indices per atom. Statistically significant relationships were found for both cases involving the local atomic properties of several atoms. For these atoms we have suggested possible interactions that could be tested by experimentalists using different substituents.

Keywords Dopamine, D₁ receptor, D₅ receptor, Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method, QSAR, receptor affinity, molecular interactions, Hartree-Fock local atomic reactivity indices, chemical reactivity

Introduction

Dopamine is a monoamine catecholamine neurotransmitter that binds to the dopamine receptors and has numerous different functions. There are five different dopamine receptors named D₁-D₅. Mishra, Singh and Shukla summarized the functions of these receptors [1]: The D₁ receptor is involved in locomotion, learning and memory, attention, impulse control, sleep and regulation of renal function. The D₂ receptor is involved in locomotion, learning and memory, attention, sleep and reproductive behaviour. The D₃ receptor is involved in locomotion, cognition, attention, impulse control, sleep and regulation of food intake. The D₄ receptor is involved in cognition, impulse control, attention, sleep and reproductive behavior. The D₅ receptor is involved in cognition, attention, decision making, motor learning and renin secretion [1]. They are divided in two categories. D₁ and D₅ receptors belong to the D₁-like subfamily of G protein-coupled receptors that are coupled to G_s alpha subunit and mediate excitatory neurotransmission. D₂, D₃ and D₄ receptors constitute the D₂-like subfamily of G protein-coupled receptors that are coupled to G_i/G_o and mediate inhibitory neurotransmission.

The importance of these receptors has led to the synthesis and testing for dopamine receptors affinities of a large amount of molecules. In our laboratory we have analyzed the electronic determinants of the dopamine receptor affinity for several molecules and receptors [2-8]. Recently, Harding et al. reported the synthesis and dopamine D₁ and D₅ receptor affinities of a group of ring C ortho halogenated 1-phenylbenzazepines [9].

Here we report the first results of a quantum chemical search of formal quantitative relationships between electronic structure and the above reported affinities.

Methods, Models and Calculations

The Method

The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez QSAR equation was developed in several steps longtime ago. As it was fully reviewed, we present only the version employed in this study. The details can be found in the literature. It is a linear relationship involving local atomic reactivity indices of the atoms composing the molecule under study. Then, for any biological activity K we have [10-21]:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(K) = & a + b \log(M_D) + \sum_{o=1}^{\text{sub}} \varphi_o + \sum_{i=1}^Y \left[e_i Q_i + f_i S_i^E + s_i S_i^N \right] + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^Y \sum_{m=(\text{HOMO}-2)^*,i}^{(\text{HOMO})^*,i} \left[h_i(m) F_i(m^*) + j_i(m) S_i^E(m^*) \right] + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^Y \sum_{m=(\text{LUMO})^*,i}^{(\text{LUMO}+2)^*,i} \left[r_i(m') F_i(m'^*) + t_i(m') S_i^N(m'^*) \right] + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^Y \left[g_i \mu_i^* + k_i \eta_i^* + o_i \omega_i^* + z_i \zeta_i^* + w_j Q_i^{*,\text{max}} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where K is a biological activity, M_D is the drug's mass and φ_o is the orientational parameter of the o -th substituent (the summation runs over all the substituents selected for the research). Q_i is the net charge of atom i and S_i^E and S_i^N are, respectively, the total atomic electrophilic and nucleophilic superdelocalizabilities of atom i . F_{i,m^*} is the electron population of atom i in occupied (empty) local MO m^* (m'^*), $S_i^E(m^*)$ is the orbital electrophilic superdelocalizability at occupied local MO m^* of atom i and $S_i^N(m'^*)$ is the orbital nucleophilic superdelocalizability at empty local MO m'^* of atom i . μ_i^* , η_i^* , ω_i^* , ζ_i^* and $Q_i^{*,\text{max}}$ are, respectively, the local atomic electronic chemical potential, the local atomic hardness, the local atomic electrophilicity, the local atomic softness and the maximal amount of electronic charge that atom i may accept. These indices were developed within the Hartree-Fock formalism. The molecular orbitals with an asterisk are the Local Molecular Orbitals (LMO) of each atom. For atom x , the LMOs are defined as the subset of the molecule's MOs having an electron population greater than 0.01e on x . In this study we have considered the three highest occupied local MOs ((HOMO)*, (HOMO-1)*, (HOMO-2)*) and the three lowest empty local MOs ((LUMO)*, (LUMO+1)*, (LUMO+2)*) of each atom because experimental evidence indicates that they are determinant for molecular reactivity. The index Y in the summations runs over all atoms composing the molecule. Good results were obtained for different molecular systems and biological activities [22-38].

Selection of Molecules and Biological Activities

The selected molecules are a group of 1-phenylbenzazepines selected from a recent study [9]. Their general formula and biological activity are displayed, respectively, in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1: General formulas of 1-phenylbenzazepines

Table 1: 1-phenylbenzazepines and dopamine receptor affinities

Mol.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	log(K) D ₁	log(K) D ₅
1	Me	H	H	H	2.1	2.49
2	Me	H	H	Cl	2.17	2.68
3	Me	H	Cl	Cl	1.88	1.4
4	Me	H	H	Br	1.86	1.91
5	H	H	H	Br	1.41	1.83
6	Me	Me	H	Cl	1.15	1.67
7	Me	Me	Cl	Cl	2.16	1.69
8	Me	Me	H	Br	1.2	1.67
9	Me	Allyl	H	Cl	1.68	2.42
10	Me	Allyl	Cl	Cl	3.02	2.68
11	Me	Allyl	H	Br	1.61	2.69
12	H	Me	H	Br	1.77	2.35
13	H	Allyl	H	Br	2.12	2.65

Figure 2 shows the histogram of frequencies for log(K) D₁ data [39]

Figure 2: Histogram of frequencies for log(K) D₁ data

We can see that the experimentalists obtained experimental D₁ data spanning about two orders of magnitude but with an empty interval between the values of log(K) 2.2 and 3. This fact is appreciated better in the next plot. Figure 3 shows the Box-Whiskers plot of log(K) D₁ values with median and quartile values.

Figure 3: Box-Whiskers plot of $\log(K)$ D_1 values [39]

We can see that the larger value of $\log(K)$ is shown as being an outlier. This effect is due only to the lacking of experimental data in the abovementioned interval. Figure 4 shows the histogram of frequencies for $\log(K)$ D_5 data.

Figure 4: Histogram of frequencies for $\log(K)$ D_5 data

In this case we can see that the data is more homogeneous in the sense that no large empty intervals exist. Figure 5 shows the Box-Whiskers plot of $\log(K)$ D_5 values with median and quartile values.

Figure 5: Box-Whiskers plot of $\log(K)$ D_5 values

In this case no outliers or extremes appear in the plot.

Calculations

The electronic structure of all molecules was calculated within the Density Functional Theory at the B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level with full geometry optimization [40]. The Gaussian 16 software was employed [41]. All the data needed to calculate the numerical values for the local atomic reactivity indices was obtained from the Gaussian results with the D-Cent-QSAR software [42]. All the electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01e were considered as being zero. Negative MO electron populations and MO populations greater than 2 coming from Mulliken Population Analysis were corrected [43]. Since the resolution of the system of linear equations is not possible because we have not sufficient molecules, we made use of Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) techniques to find the best solution. For each case, a matrix containing the dependent variable ($\log(K)$ in this case) and the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of the common skeleton as independent variables was built. The Statistica software was used [39].

Now, let us consider the following problem. We are dealing with a group of molecules, some with different number of atoms and some with substituents placed at different places. On the other hand, Eq. 1 must have the same number of atoms in the system of equations. To satisfy this mandatory condition, the logical way to proceed is to select atoms having an equivalent one in all the molecules. The chemical nature of the equivalent atoms does not need to be the same (for example, in one molecule the atom is carbon while in another molecule it can be nitrogen). This set of atoms is called the common skeleton and it is hypothesized that it accounts for almost all the interactions leading to the expression of a given biological activity. It is more or less obvious that this skeleton could have different sizes. The common skeleton for this case is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Common skeleton of 1-phenylbenzazepines derivatives

Results

Results for D₁ receptor binding affinity

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(K) = 2.55 + 0.29S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* - 20.00F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^* - 0.44\mu_{18}^* + 0.55\mu_8^* \quad (2)$$

with $n=13$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.96$, $F(4,8)=64.692$ ($p < 0.00000$) and $SD=0.10$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 17, $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the electron population of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 8, μ_{18}^* is the local atomic electronic potential of atom 18 and μ_8^* is the local atomic electronic potential of atom 8 [17]. Tables 2 and 3 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 2. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 3). Figure 7 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated values.

Table 2: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 2

Var.	Beta	t(8)	p-level
$S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	0.74	11.56	0.000003
$F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-0.58	-8.92	0.00002
μ_{18}^*	-0.32	-5.09	0.0009
μ_8^*	0.26	3.96	0.004

Table 3: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 2

	$S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	$F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	μ_{18}^*	μ_8^*
$S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	1.00			
$F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	0.00	1.00		
μ_{18}^*	0.03	0.03	1.00	
μ_8^*	0.05	0.07	0.01	1.00

Figure 7: Plot of predicted *vs.* observed $\log(K)$ values (Eq. 2). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 2 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms constituting the common skeleton explains about 96% of the variation of the numerical values of $\log(K)$. Figure 7, spanning about 2 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values. Figures 8, 9 and 10 show, respectively, the plot of predicted values *vs.* residuals scores, the plot of residual *vs.* deleted residuals and the normal probability plot of residuals.

Figure 8: Plot of predicted values *vs.* residuals scores

The plot shows no indication of any kind of ordering. Then this plot supports the idea that the linear equation is a good first approach to study these molecular systems.

Figure 9: Plot of residual vs. deleted residuals

In this case we have one point localized very far from the confidence interval, strongly suggesting that this molecule has one or more interactions with the binding site through atoms not belonging to the common skeleton. This point deserves further research.

Figure 10: Normal probability plot of residuals

These three plots show that the linear equation 2 is a good starting point for a QSAR analysis.

Results for D₅ receptor binding affinity

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(K) = 2.64 - 21.80F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^* + 2.09Q_{18}^{*\max} - 2.06F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^* \quad (3)$$

with $n=13$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.91$, $F(3,9)=44.038$ ($p<0.00001$) and $SD=0.14$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the electron population of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 8, $Q_{18}^{*\max}$ is the maximal amount of charge atom 18 may receive and $F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the electron population of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 1. Tables 4 and 5 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 3. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 5). Figure 11 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated values.

Table 4: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 3

Var.	Beta	t(9)	p-level
$F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-21.80	-7.63	0.00003
$Q_{18}^{*\max}$	2.09	4.39	0.002
$F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-2.06	-3.68	0.005

Table 5: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 3

	$F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	$Q_{18}^{*\text{max}}$	$F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$
$F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	1.00		
$Q_{18}^{*\text{max}}$	0.02	1.00	
$F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	0.00	0.20	1.00

Figure 11: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(K)$ values (Eq. 3). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 3 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of three local atomic reactivity indices of atoms constituting the common skeleton explains about 91% of the variation of $\log(K)$. Figure 11, spanning about 1.2 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a relatively good correlation of observed versus calculated values. Figures 12, 13 and 14 show, respectively, the plot of predicted values vs. residuals scores, the plot of residual vs. deleted residuals and the normal probability plot of residuals.

Figure 12: Plot of predicted values vs. residuals scores

No indication of a pattern is observed.

Figure 13: Plot of residual vs. deleted residuals

Almost all points are inside the confidence interval or very close to it.

Figure 14: Normal probability plot of residuals

These three plots are a clear support to the hypothesis stating that linear Eq. 3 is a reliable tool to use for the analysis.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 6 shows the local MO structure of atoms 1, 8, 17 and 18 (see Fig. 6). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO)/(HOMO-2)*(HOMO-1)*(HOMO)*- (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 6: The local MO structure of atoms 1, 8, 17 and 18

Mol.	Atom 1	Atom 8	Atom 17	Atom 18
1 (72)	70π71π72π- 74π75π76π	70σ71σ72σ- 76σ81σ83σ	69π70π71π- 73π74π76π	62σ67σ71σ- 77σ78σ79σ
2 (80)	74π78π80π- 83π84π85π	75σ79σ80σ- 84σ87σ88σ	77π78π79π- 81π82π84π	68σ69σ79σ- 86σ 87σ88σ
3 (88)	81σ86π88π- 91π92π93π	83σ87σ88σ- 93σ96σ98σ	84π85π86π- 89π90π91σ	75σ76σ87σ- 95σ96σ97σ
4 (89)	84π87π89π- 92π93π94π	86σ88σ89σ- 96σ97σ99σ	86π87π88π- 90π91π93σ	76σ78σ88σ- 95σ96σ97σ
5 (85)	80π83π85π- 88π90π91σ	82σ84σ85σ- 90σ94σ95σ	82π83π84π- 86π87π89σ	73σ75σ84σ- 91σ92σ93σ

6 (84)	82π83π84π- 87π88π89π	82σ83σ84σ- 88σ94σ96σ	81π82π83π- 85π86π88π	73σ77σ83σ- 91σ94σ98σ
7 (92)	90π91π92π- 95π96π97π	90σ91σ92σ- 97σ102σ103σ	88π89π90π- 93π94π95σ	80σ85σ91σ- 100σ102σ107σ
8 (93)	91π92π93π- 96π97π98π	88σ92σ93σ- 97σ103σ104σ	89π90π91π- 94π95π97σ	82σ85σ92σ- 100σ103σ105σ
9 (91)	89π90π91π- 94π95π96π	89σ90σ91σ- 95σ96σ102σ	87π88π89π- 92π93π96π	86σ90σ91σ- 95σ100σ102σ
10 (99)	97π98π99π- 102π103π104π	94σ98σ99σ- 103σ105σ106σ	95π96π97π- 100π101π10σ	91σ94σ98σ- 103σ104σ108σ
11	94π98π99π- (100) 103π104π105π	98σ99σ100σ- 104σ106σ107σ	96π97π98π- 101π102π10σ	92σ95σ100σ- 105σ109σ111σ
12 (89)	87π88π89π- 92π93π94π	87σ88σ89σ- 93σ94σ99σ	85π86π87π- 90π91π93σ	79σ81σ89σ- 97σ102σ104σ
13 (96)	90π94π95π- 99π100π101π	94σ95σ96σ- 100σ102σ103σ	92π93π94π- 97π98π100σ	88σ91σ96σ- 101σ106σ107σ

Discussion

Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP)

Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) maps allow determining which sectors of the molecule are nucleophiles or electrophiles. Also, they enable us to visualize the charge-related properties of molecules at a certain distance of the nuclei, and they are useful for detecting the similitudes and differences in the MEPs and provide a first idea about how the molecules approach the site. Here we present the MEP maps of the most and less active molecules for each one of the receptors, calculated at 4.5 Å of the nuclei [44].

In the case of D1 receptor, figures 15 and 16 show, respectively, the MEP map of molecules 6 (the most active) and 10 (the less active) calculated at 4.5 Å of the nuclei.

Figure 15: MEP map of molecule 6 (left and right are rotated views)

Figure 16: MEP map of molecule 10 (left and right are rotated views)

In the case of D_5 receptor figures 17 and 18 show, respectively, the MEP map of molecules 3 (left, the most active) and 11 (right, the less active) calculated at 4.5 Å of the nuclei.

Figure 17: MEP map of molecule 3 (left and right are rotated views)

Figure 18: MEP map of molecule 11 (left and right are rotated views)

We can see that there are some differences in the MEP maps for the four molecules, but they are not enough significant allowing suggesting a structure-activity relationship.

Figure 19 shows the MEP maps of molecules 6 and 10 [45].

Figure 19: MEP of molecules 6 (left) and 10 (right). The red surface corresponds to negative MEP values (-0.0004) and the yellow surface to positive MEP values (0.0004).

Figure 20 shows the MEP maps of molecules 3 and 11.

Figure 20: MEP of molecules 3 (left) and 11 (right). The red surface corresponds to negative MEP values (-0.0004) and the yellow surface to positive MEP values (0.0004).

In these figures we may appreciate several differences in the MEP maps. At short distances the map's structure is strongly influenced by the kind of substituents but it is only possible to state some generalizations such as the possibility of an H-bond, a pi-pi interaction, etc.

Discussion of the results for D₁ receptor binding affinity [46, 47]

Table 2 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 2 is $S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > \mu_{18}^* > \mu_8^*$. A high D₁ receptor affinity is associated with low numerical values for $S_{17}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$, large numerical values for $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$, small (negative) values for μ_{18}^* and large (negative) numerical values for μ_8^* . The atoms appearing in Eq. 2 are shown in figure 21.

Figure 21: Atoms appearing in Eq. 2.

Atom 8 is a sp^3 carbon atom in ring B (Fig. 6). Two local atomic reactivity indices belonging to this atom appear in Eq. 2: $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ and μ_8^* . All local MOs have a sigma nature. Large numerical values for $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ are associated with a higher receptor affinity. The only way to obtain these values is by increasing the electron population on it, i.e., by limiting the localization of this MO to atom 8. This will make this local MO more prone to interact with electron-rich centers or with anions. On the other hand, larger (negative) numerical values for μ_8^* are also associated with high receptor affinity. Knowing that μ_8^* is the midpoint between the local $(\text{HOMO})_8^*$ energy

and the local $(LUMO)_8^*$ energy, the only way to get these large negative values is by lowering the $(LUMO)_8^*$ energy or by lowering the $(HOMO)_8^*$ energy (or by both procedures carried out at the same time). In the first case we obtain a more reactive $(LUMO)_8^*$ and in the other a less reactive $(HOMO)_8^*$. $(HOMO)_8^*$ coincides with the molecular HOMO. $(LUMO)_8^*$ coincides with empty molecular MOs other than LUMO in all cases. These two local atomic reactivity indices are coincident when we think that atom 8 should be interacting with an electron-rich center or with an anion. The most probable interactions are the alkyl ones. Atom 18 is the first atom of the substituent bonded to N9 (H or C, see Table 1 and Fig. 6). Table 6 shows that all local MO have a sigma nature. Small (negative) values for μ_{18}^* are associated with high receptor affinity. These values can be obtained by shifting upwards the $(HOMO)_{18}^*$ and/or the $(LUMO)_{18}^*$ energies. In the first case we have a better electron donor and in the second a bad electron acceptor. If we consider the hydrogen atom, the interaction with the site could be through a N9-H18...X (X= N, O) hydrogen bond. When X18 is carbon (sp^3 in all cases) it is possible to suggest alkyl interactions. It seems that it is not possible to suggest a common interaction site for H and C. Atom 17 is a sp^2 carbon atom in ring C (Fig. 6). Table 6 shows that the local $(LUMO)^*$ coincides with the molecular LUMO in all cases and that the local $(HOMO)^*$ coincides with molecular orbitals close to the molecular HOMO in all cases. Low numerical values for $S_{17}^N(LUMO+2)^*$ are associated with high receptor affinity. These values can be obtained by shifting upwards the energies of $(LUMO+2)_{17}^*$ making this MO less reactive. Applying the rule we established earlier, $(LUMO+1)_{17}^*$ and $(LUMO)_{17}^*$ energies should be also shifted upwards, making atom 17 a bad electron acceptor. Therefore, it is possible to suggest that atom 17 will be prone to interact with electron-deficient sites or with cations. Table 6 shows that the three highest occupied local MOs have a pi nature. Therefore possible interactions of atom 17 are π -cation, π - π , and/or π -alkyl [46, 47]. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 22.

Figure 22: Partial 2D pharmacophore (D_1)

Discussion of the results for D_5 receptor binding affinity

Table 4 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 3 is $F_8(LUMO+2)^* \gg Q_{18}^{*max} > F_1(LUMO+2)^*$. The atoms appearing in Eq. 3 are shown in figure 23.

Figure 23: Atoms appearing in Eq. 3

A high D_5 receptor affinity is associated with large numerical values for $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$, small numerical values for $Q_{18}^{*\text{max}}$ and large numerical values for $F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. Atom 8 is a sp^3 carbon in ring B. As high receptor affinities are associated with large numerical values for $F_8(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ like in the D_1 results, all what was mentioned above applies here. Atom 18 is the first atom of the substituent bonded to N9 (H or C, see Table 1 and Fig. 6). A high D_5 receptor affinity is associated with small numerical values for $Q_{18}^{*\text{max}}$. This requirement indicates that atom 18 should not be a good charge acceptor and we may enhance this effect by shifting upwards the $(\text{LUMO})_{18}^*$ energy. Like the previous case, we cannot find a common interaction site for H and C atoms. If the H atoms are bad electron acceptors we may suggest a strong $\text{N9}\dots\text{H18}\dots\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{N}, \text{O}$) hydrogen bond. In the case of a C18 atom we can suggest alkyl interactions. A possible strategy to deal with this problem is to do an analysis with molecules in which X18 all substituents have more than one atom in order to enlarge the common skeleton. This requires a larger number of molecules. Atom 1 is a sp^2 carbon in ring A (see Fig. 6). Larger numerical values for $F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ are associated with a higher D_5 receptor affinity. Table 6 shows that the three highest occupied and the three lowest empty local MOs have a pi nature. Larger numerical values for $F_1(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ are obtained is by increasing the electron population on it, i.e., by limiting the localization of this MO to atom 1. This will make this local MO more prone to interact with electron-rich centers or with anions. Using the rules stated about the appearance of MOs other than the frontier ones we suggest that $(\text{LUMO}+1)_1^*$ and $(\text{LUMO})_1^*$ must also increase their reactivity. Therefore, atom 1 could be involved in π -anion, π - π and/or π -alkyl interactions [46, 47]. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 24.

Figure 24: Partial 2D pharmacophore (D_5)

In summary, for series of 1-phenylbenzazepines we have obtained statistically significant relationships between the electronic structure and dopamine D_1 and D_5 receptor affinities. For the atoms appearing to be involved in the drug-receptor interaction we have suggested possible interactions that could be tested by experimentalists.

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